

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

Ocean salinity analysis practices: How to get the most out of bottle salinity samples

Instructional Presentation

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Outline of the Presentation

I. Why measure bottle salinity? ... Okay, how? ... But really, how?

II. Different approaches to:

- I. Collecting and storing samples
- II. Measuring bottle conductivity and standardising using IAPSO standard seawater
- III. Applying bottle salinity to calibrate CTD and underway conductivity sensors

III. Recommendations

- I. Collecting and storing samples
- II. Measuring bottle conductivity and standardising using IAPSO standard seawater

Firing et al., 2024, [EuroGO-SHIP D3.3: Report on updated salinity best practice](#)

Why

Why measure bottle salinity when we have CTDs (and TSGs)?

- Accurate and consistent measurements of salinity are essential for understanding the ocean's role in climate, ecosystems, and human activities
- CTD conductivity sensors drift, often with pressure dependence; this can be a significant source of error to:
 - Estimates of small trends in deep waters
 - Calculations of parameters sensitive to salinity (including in the ocean carbonate system and in air-sea-ice exchanges)
- Collecting discrete bottle samples and analysing their salinity in the lab, with reference to standard seawater, is important for updating CTD sensor calibration and improving data quality from each cruise
- Even cruises whose primary focus is not ocean physics or repeat hydrography can contribute to the global dataset of continuing observations with well-quantified uncertainty that we need to understand our changing oceans

How

- **Collect samples from CTD Niskin bottles and/or the surface underway uncontaminated seawater supply**
 - *Sample bottles are rinsed, filled leaving a small headspace, and sealed to prevent evaporation*
- **Use a salinometer to precisely and accurately measure conductivity of each sample at a known temperature**

Salinometers work by:

- Drawing a small volume subsample from a salinity sample bottle into a cell of the instrument
 - *A strong peristaltic pump, or a rubber bung to seal the top of the sample bottle, reduces opportunity for evaporation*
- Heating or cooling the subsample to a set temperature
 - *Uses a water bath whose temperature is maintained by switching lamps on and off; more efficient when it needs to heat the subsample than when it needs to cool it*
 - *The whole sample bottle may also be immersed in a larger bath, if available*
 - *Temperature of the bath may be monitored or may just be set using a thermostat*
- Measuring the subsample's conductivity relative to a reference conductivity
 - *Manufacturer-supplied software records the conductivity ratio over a time interval*
- **Adjust for any offsets in the salinometer itself by also measuring IAPSO-certified standard seawater**
- **Convert to salinity using the known temperature and the equation of state for seawater**

How

How many samples do I need to collect?

- **Collect samples from CTD Niskin bottles and/or the surface underway uncontaminated seawater supply**
 - *Sample bottles are rinsed, filled leaving a small headspace, and sealed to prevent evaporation*

What kind of salinometer?

- **Use a salinometer to precisely and accurately measure conductivity of each sample at a known temperature**

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How often do I have to do this?

How (specifically)

How many samples? What about standardisation?

Approaches to samples	“We send the CTD for factory calibration regularly, or even before and after the cruise, so we don’t need samples.”	“Salinity is known from the CTD, so we just collect a few samples per cruise to apply a constant offset. Samples are probably stored for analysis on shore, possibly in a multi-cruise batch.”	“Samples from most of the Niskins, which are almost all in the upper ocean.” OR “Samples only from deep Niskins where the background gradient is low.”	“GO-SHIP best practice: all Niskins from every cast, distributed over the full depth, analysed on board. Underway samples every few hours for the TSG.”
Approaches to standardisation	“N/A”	“Standardise the salinometer from time to time, apply whatever remaining offset it displays to the sample measurements.”	“Standardise the salinometer on installation and measure a new bottle of standard seawater daily, re-standardise if offset outside tolerance.”	“Standardise the salinometer on installation and measure a new bottle of standard seawater before and after each batch of 24 samples, using offsets over time to correct for salinometer drift.”

Lower accuracy, lower cost

Higher accuracy, higher cost

Impacts	Sensor calibration does not always change linearly, shipping may be an issue; factory calibration is a complement to collecting bottle samples, not a substitute.	Calibration depends on time and pressure, so samples should be taken from the full range of depths and throughout the cruise. The salinity-conductivity relationship depends on temperature, so they should also be taken from a range of temperatures. Background ocean variability adds noise to the comparison between sensor data and bottle data; more samples may be needed to reduce uncertainty. Salinometer standardisation can also drift and fluctuate; more monitoring reduces bias as well as potential wasted samples (if there are issues with the salinometer).	Person-time required for analysis (e.g. >1 hour per cast). Expense of standard seawater. Water budgets may be limiting especially as measurements of trace elements and of biological parameters become more common.
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How (specifically)

What are the most efficient things to do to get the highest quality data given our constraints on standard seawater purchases, staff time, equipment and lab space at sea, and other demands on Niskin water and/or sample distribution?

- Take more samples (if you can) and prioritise their distribution if not
 - For calibration, sample over a range of depths, especially from points with low background gradient
- Get the most out of each sample by following good sample collection and analysis practices

How (specifically)

What are the most efficient things to do to get the highest quality data given our constraints on standard seawater purchases, staff time, equipment and lab space at sea, and other demands on Niskin water and/or sample distribution?

- Take more samples (if you can) and prioritise their distribution if not
 - For calibration, sample over a range of depths, especially from points with low background gradient
- Get the most out of each sample by following good sample collection and analysis practices
 - Common sampling mistakes to avoid:
 - *Contamination from splashes or rain*
 - *Leaving too much, or too little, headspace in the sample bottle*
 - *Rinsing the bottle caps in Niskin water, or contaminating the sample with salty hands*
 - *Not properly sealing sample bottles*
 - *Storing samples for more than 4 months*

How (specifically)

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- Take more samples (if you can) and prioritise their distribution if not
 - For calibration, sample over a range of depths, especially from points with low background gradient
- Get the most out of each sample by following good sample collection and analysis practices
 - Maintain the salinometer
 - Try to maintain consistent ambient, sample, and salinometer temperature
 - *Monitor ambient and salinometer temperature if possible*
 - *Consider using an external water bath to equilibrate bottle samples*
 - Always use a newly-unsealed, in-date bottle of standard seawater to determine standardisation offset
 - *Use more than one bottle of standard seawater to standardise the salinometer*
 - *Monitor and record changes in standardisation offset using more bottles of standard seawater throughout, ideally at least two per analysis day*
 - *Record measurements from 3-4 replicate subsamples from each bottle (sample and standard)*

Thank you

Salinity sampling and analysis procedures:

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EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

EuroGO-SHIP focused on enabling the European community conducting hydrographic observations at sea to provide higher quality and more sustainable data flows to a broad range of end users, more effectively.

The project worked toward strengthening European capabilities to deliver world-class Oceanographic science, which is key to informing policies and to meet the goals of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” and the wider objectives of the EU Green Deal.

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